

This is a template to support the analysis and assurance of the Data Quality. It is divided into three different parts: a first section providing guidance for identification of low-quality data causes, a second section supporting the creation of Data Quality Indicators (DQI), and a third section to support the definition of actions to be done to improve the data quality. Once you filled your template, please upload it to your NextCloud project folder.

Keepers of the sea / Water Sentinels

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Cause-effect diagram (optional)

Starting from the question “what are the main variables that affect the quality of my data?” try to fill the table inserting different points for each of the “6M” characteristics: man, machine, material, method, mother nature, measurement.

This activity is optional, but it can be very helpful to investigate in depth the causes which leads to low-quality data. If such causes are already very clear, this section can be skipped.

The operational and/or functional labor of people engaged	Facilities, systems, tools, and equipment employed, etc.	Raw materials, components, consumables used, etc.	Processes and services	Environmental uncontrollable and/or predictable events	physical measurement, automatic sensor readings, and inspections
Man	Machine	Material	Method	Mother nature	Measurement
<i>Eg: volunteers training level, missing communication</i>	<i>Eg: devices</i>	<i>Eg: consumables needed for measures</i>	<i>Eg: training process, is your methodology based on scientific evidence?</i>	<i>Eg: weather conditions to collect data</i>	<i>Eg: subjective evaluation scales</i>
People’s memories are not accurate at reporting water pollution events Low digital literacy of	At the field: GPS without batteries; At the laboratory: There is always an error associated	Sampling kits are not seen as useful for the participants (e.g. too heavy for them to carry, difficult to maintain on a boat)	Training process is not efficient at showing participants the importance of following each step	Environmental conditions does not allow for good water sampling according to experimental procedure	Readings of the secchi depth and/or water temperature made wrong (e.g. just one measurement of temp; reading of secchi disc with sun reflection on water and/or

participants can compromise accuracy of data from the “source” to the databases	with the equipment used for assessing water parameters			Public health issues related to pandemic does not allow for the historical data questionnaire to be properly applied in person with the community	interference from boat propeller

Data Quality Indicators

Select the relevant dimensions from the ones listed below, and for each of them find one or more Data Quality Indicators (quantifiable) related to your project (see examples). Then, for each indicator define at least one quality control activity (used to assess the indicator), a goal (which would define the minimum quality acceptable for that indicator). In the last column, insert the last measure collected from the activity (or your best estimation of the status of the indicator), to see if the goal is satisfied or further actions are needed.

The table lists a complete set of dimensions, with the first five in bold as they are the most relevant from literature. Depending on your pilot, some dimensions could have the same meaning, and some others could be not applicable in your case. Feel free to use only the ones representative for your project.

Data Quality Indicators can be properly defined also considering the previous table of the 6M (e.g., “volunteers training level” listed above, inspires the indicator “Percentage of volunteers with a sufficient knowledge”, under the dimension “Consistency”). Please note that not all the causes impact on Data Quality with the same weight: in the analysis try to address those causes which have the main impact.

Data quality dimensions	Data Quality Indicators	Quality control activities and checks	DQI goal	Current/last quantification
	<i>Eg: Percentage of data coming from the different areas of the Region (north, south, east, west)</i>	<i>Eg: Monthly check of measurements locations</i>	<i>Eg: > 15% of data from each Region</i>	<i>Eg: 10% from south, 50% from north, 20% from east, 20% from west</i>
1. Completeness	Percentage of sampling locations in accordance to what is expected from historical data and participants’ fishing areas	Monthly check on the current sampling locations (Jun-Aug)	By the end of the pilot >50% of current data sampling locations (10) are on the historical pollution locations and participants’ fishing areas	

ACTION

2. Accuracy	<i>Eg: Calibration vs measurements ratio</i>	<i>Eg: Periodic control of calibrations and measurements (monthly?)</i>	<i>Eg: > 80%</i>	<i>Eg: Only 75% of the measurements happens after a calibration</i>
	Percentage of data obtained from water sample analyses on the laboratory is within expected range taking into account callibration of equipment and methodology (use of blank samples and comparison to previous scientific data)	Monthly assessment of measurements with project partners (comparison to previous and/or expected data); check for outliers	15 out of 20 samples show water quality parameters within what is expected	
3. Timeliness	<i>Eg: Percentage of sampling stations with latest data older than 2 weeks</i>	<i>Eg: periodic check of data coming from sampling stations</i>	<i>Eg: < 10%</i>	<i>Eg: 5% of the sampling stations do not have updated data</i>
	Number of water samples collected by month, to assure data are consistently collected within a 3 month period	Monthly check with participants about water sampling tasks	20 pilot samples are collected in May-July, according to the experimental plan	
4. Consistency	<i>Eg: Percentage of volunteers with a sufficient knowledge</i>	<i>Eg: Evaluation of volunteers' knowledge</i>	<i>Eg: 80%</i>	<i>Eg: 90% well executed the test</i>
	Percentage of participants trained and performing well at their project tasks	Monthly assess participants performance at water collection tasks and pollution events ID	4 out of 5 participants are effectively trained and show good performance at their tasks	
Accessibility				
5. Amount of data	Percentage of data successfully collected by all participants and project team: we expect	Monthly check on data collected	At least 75% of the expected data is collected and validated by the	

ACTION

	water quality parameters to be obtained from 20 water samples collected by 5 trained participants and 20 questionnaires for historical data to be applied by the project team		project team as good quality	
<i>Believability</i>				
<i>Concise representation</i>				
<i>Consistent representation</i>				
<i>Currency</i>				
<i>Free-of-error</i>				
<i>Interpretability</i>				
<i>Objectivity</i>				
<i>Precision</i>				
<i>Relevance</i>				
<i>Reputation</i>				
<i>Security</i>				
<i>Understandability</i>				
<i>Validity</i>				

Value-added				

Improvement activities

For each DQI indicated in the first table (especially those for which the goal is not reached), try to imagine one or more activities to improve the DQI. One activity might involve more than one DQI, as well as it is possible that multiple actions are needed for a single DQI. For each activity, indicate a deadline and a responsible to guarantee that the action will be taken into account and it will be concluded.

Improvement activity	Timeline	Responsible	Involved DQI
<i>E.g.: Implement automatic measurements rejection if the measurement tool has not been calibrated in the last 4 times.</i>	<i>E.g.: 3 months (within June 2021)</i>	<i>E.g.: IT department</i>	<i>E.g.: Calibration vs measurements ratio</i>
<i>E.g.: Training of the volunteers</i>	<i>E.g.: 2 months (within May 2021)</i>	<i>E.g.: Pilot manager</i>	<i>E.g.: Volunteers' skill level measurement</i>
For DQI 1 (completeness) we need to obtain feedback from the participants and project team on two topics, in the beginning of the project: a) expected pollution events locations and b) participants' usual fishing areas	May-July 2021	OA Team	Percentage of sampling locations in accordance to what is expected from historical data and participants' fishing areas
For DQI 2 (accuracy) close communication between OA team and researchers (IPS team) is needed, to assure the data is in accordance to what expected when equipment's and methodologies are calibrated and tested; first samples to be analyzed will be blanks, so the methodology can be tested	May-July 2021	IPS Team	Percentage of data obtained from water sample analyses on the laboratory is within expected range taking into account callibration of equipment and methodology (use of blank samples and comparison to previous scientific data)
For DQI 3 (timeliness) an experimental plan will be set-up to prepare data sampling frequency during the project	June 2021	OA Team	Number of water samples collected by month, to assure data are consistently collected within a 3 month period

For DQI 4 (consistency), when participants are trained, the first water collection will be made under project team supervision; a close contact with participants in all data collection events (by phone) will contribute to data consistency	May-July 2021	OA Team	Percentage of participants trained and performing well at their project tasks
For DQI 5 (amount of data), by the end of the project a classification system for data quality will be applied (1-5 rating) based on the feedback of participants, project team and researchers	August 2021	OA Team	Percentage of data successfully collected by all participants and project team: we expect water quality parameters to be obtained from 20 water samples collected by 5 trained participants and 20 questionnaires for historical data to be applied by the project team

Notes

In this space personalize your Data Quality Assessment plan.